

1. **Make** a GitHub Account and connect to Utrecht University.

See <https://github.com/UtrechtUniversity/getting-started>.

2. **Create** a new repository.

3. **Upload** your code and/or scripts.

Findability

- Create a **README** in **GitHub** that introduces your code and analysis. See the template on the back.
- Get a DOI for your repository by uploading a persistent copy to archiving tool **Zenodo**

- Use **ORCID** identifier(s) in your **Zenodo metadata**. You don't have one yet? Go to orcid.org and sign up.

read Accessibility Interoperability Reusability first before publishing the result

README template on the back!

Accessibility

- Does your code contain **privacy sensitive information** or other information that cannot be disclosed?

Interoperability

Add the following information to your **README file**:

- Include any necessary **prerequisites** for using your code, such as required datasets, specific (open) software, dependencies or hardware requirements.
- If applicable, provide clear instructions how to get the **input data**.

- Use an open programming language that is **common** or **rising** in your research domain.
- Use input and output formats for data that are open protocols. For example, the CSV format.

Reusability

- Publish your code under an accessible **license**. Do you want to publish your code fully **open** or with (some) **restrictions**?

Add the following information to your **README file**:

- Provide **documentation** and **examples** on using your **code**.
- Enable users to **contact** you (e.g. GitHub) in case they have questions, remarks, or **feature requests**.

Interested in more on FAIR code?

Visit uu.nl/rdm for guides, workshops, and walk-in hours. Or contact our experts at info.rdm@uu.nl.

Your code is now FAIR and ready to be published!

README template

README.md

Title of your code or analysis

In this section, provide an overview of your code and describe the project in which the code was developed. Highlight the purpose, scope, and potential uses of your code.

Prerequisites

Include any necessary prerequisites for using your code, such as required datasets, specific software, dependencies or hardware requirements. For example: This project requires Python 3.8 or later and install the dependencies with `pip install -r requirements.txt`.

Contents

Describe the organization of your package, including the contents of each folder and the files it contains. Describe where results and figures are stored if not added to the project folder.

Usage

Provide clear and concise instructions on how to use your code. Include examples of how to execute the code. If your work consists of multiple execution steps, provide detailed step-by-step instructions.

License

With an open-source license, such as MIT, GPL3, and Apache 2.0, you grant permission to use your work. Choose a license that aligns with your goals for your code.

For example: This work is licensed under the MIT License.

Citation (optional)

Provide clear instructions on how to cite your code or related publications in a research paper or publication. You can also add a separate CITATION.cff file.

Contact

Include contact information for questions or comments about your project. You can also provide clear instructions for how users can provide feedback, contribute, or suggest improvement to your work.

Interested in more on writing a README?

Visit uu.nl/rdm for guides, workshops, and walk-in hours. Or contact our experts at info.rdm@uu.nl.

Check out the
extended version:

<https://bit.ly/FAIR-Code-Readme>

